

Agricultural Financing and Poverty Alleviation Among Small Holder Farmers in Imo State

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Abstract: Previous studies have demonstrated that neither commercial banks nor the emerging international donors are keen to sufficiently meet the financial needs along agricultural value chains. This paper reviewed the role of agriculture financing towards poverty reduction in Imo State. The theoretical framework of the study is based on the work of Arrow et al. (2012) using the first-best resource allocation theory of the welfare economics. The study adopted descriptive research design and the population are according to the 2006 census which state that Imo state has 4,609,038 persons. The multi-stage sampling technique was used to select the samples size of the study across the three agricultural zones which is 252. The Bio-data was analyzed with descriptive statistics while multiple regressions were used to test the hypotheses. The result shows that government funding have significance relationship with standard of living ($\beta = .944$; $t = 39.966$; $P < .000$), Banks Funding have significance relationship with Asset Based ($\beta = .854$; $t = 22.998$; $P < .000$) and International Donors Funding have significance relationship with Income ($\beta = .877$; $t = 25.500$; $P < .000$). In conclusion if agricultural financing is enhanced by relevant authorities it will certainly contribute to poverty reduction among the farmers. We recommend that mechanism of enhancing economic growth through agriculture financing should be entrenched by the government and all parties involved

Keywords: Agriculture, Financing, Government Funding, Smallholder Farmers, Poverty Alleviation.

Introduction

Across the world, smallholder farming has been recognized as vital for poverty eradication, employment generation, and food security (Röttger, 2015). Agriculture remains the backbone of the global economy by ensuring food supply and providing raw materials to industries, thereby supporting Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) on poverty and hunger reduction. Central to agricultural development is agricultural finance, which determines the quality of inputs, technology, and labor available to farmers (Miller & Jones, 2010). Agricultural finance refers to financial services for production, processing, and marketing (IFC, 2011), encompassing both formal and informal sources, loans of varying durations, and leasing options. It is essentially access to and utilization of credit to enhance farm efficiency and technology adoption, with repayment plans in place (Ejiogu, 2018). In Nigeria, government interventions such as the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA), Anchor Borrowers' Programme, Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACs), and Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) were established to improve credit access (Osabohien et al., 2020). For example, between 2009 and 2016, 74% of a 200-billion-Naira intervention fund was disbursed to 191

agribusinesses, with significant allocations to crop and livestock production (Osabohien et al., 2020). Despite these efforts, credit to agriculture remains disproportionately low compared to other sectors, even though agriculture contributes more to GDP (Nevin et al., 2019). Poverty, however, extends beyond low income to include deprivation in health, education, nutrition, and security (Okuneye, 2001; Adeleke, 2012). The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 1997, 1998) measures poverty using the Human Development Index (HDI), incorporating life expectancy, education, and per-capita income. In Nigeria, successive governments have implemented poverty alleviation strategies, but limited research into root causes and ineffective monitoring have undermined outcomes. This paper, therefore, seeks to address this intellectual gap by examining agricultural financing as a pathway to poverty reduction and sustainable development.

Access to finance is essential for transforming agriculture from subsistence to commercial production, as it supports sectoral growth, poverty reduction, food security, and job creation (IFC, 2011; IISD, 2015). However, studies show that commercial banks and international donors often fail to meet financing needs across agricultural value chains. Many government interventions are short-term fixes, such as temporary job creation, which do not provide sustainable

financial services for agriculture (IFC, 2011). Unlike developed countries, agriculture in Africa remains characterized by low productivity. Without urgent interventions, the sector will not achieve its full potential (IFC, 2011; Olajide, Akinlabi & Tijani, 2012). Most African governments also spend below the 10% budgetary target for agriculture set by the CAADP Maputo Declaration of 2003 (Ali, Poomthan & Warunsiri, 2016). This financing gap for smallholder farmers underpins the rationale for this study. This research is among the first in Nigeria to examine the relationship between sources of agricultural financing and their impact on development indicators such as poverty alleviation. It aims to identify efficient ways of utilizing agricultural intervention funds for optimal benefits in reducing poverty within farming communities. The objective of this study is to examine the effect of government funding on smallholder farmers' standard of living in Imo State, assess the effect of bank funding on smallholder farmers' asset base in Imo State and determine the effect of international donor funding on smallholder farmers' income in Imo State.

Methodology

Research design

This study adopted a survey research design to gather primary data from farmers in Imo

State. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed.

Stage one

Three Local Government Areas (LGAs) were purposively selected from each of the three agricultural zones (Owerri, Orlu, and Okigwe). These included Ngor Okpala, Owerri West, and Ikeduru (Owerri zone); Ohaji-Egbema, Oru West, and Oguta (Orlu zone); Ihitte-Uboma, Onu Imo, and Isiala Mbano (Okigwe zone).

Stage two

Three autonomous communities were randomly selected from each chosen LGA.

Stage three

Four villages were randomly drawn from each community.

Stage four

Seven farmers were randomly selected from each village, yielding a sample size of 252 farmers.

Data were collected using structured questionnaires and analyzed with descriptive statistics (means, percentages, frequency distributions) and simple regression models to test the study hypotheses.

Results and Discussion

This section presents and analyzes the study data. Descriptive statistics (percentages) were

used for respondents' profiles, while regression analysis tested the hypotheses using SPSS v23.

Table 1 Questionnaire Return Rate

	Number. Distributed	Number Returned	% of Number Returned	Number not Returned	% of Number not Returned
Questionnaire	252	198	78.6%	54	21.4

Source Field Survey, 2025

Out of 252 questionnaires distributed, 198 (78.6%) were returned, while 54 (21.4%) were not.

Demographic Characteristics

Of the respondents, 117 (59.1%) were male and 81 (40.9%) female. Marital status shows 111 (56.1%) married and 87 (43.9%) single. By age, 37 (18.7%) were 20–30 years, 107 (54.0%) were 31–40 years, 40 (20.2%) were

41–50 years, and 14 (7.1%) above 50. Educationally, 28 (14.1%) had primary certificates, 53 (26.8%) WAEC/NECO, 100 (50.5%) HND/BSc, and 17 (8.6%) postgraduate degrees. Farming experience shows 56 (28.3%) with 1–10 years, 109 (55.1%) with 11–20 years, and 33 (16.7%) with 21–30 years. This indicates respondents were generally experienced and qualified.

Table 2 Responses on Government Funding

Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Government Funding 1	72	36.4	65	32.8	9	4.5	30	15.2	22	11.1
Government Funding 2	97	49.0	72	36.4	4	2.0	22	11.1	3	1.5
Government Funding 3	58	34.3	97	49.0	15	7.6	5	2.5	13	6.6
Government Funding 4	100	50.5	55	27.8	20	10.1	17	8.6	6	3.0

Most respondents agreed government funding positively influenced agriculture, with high agreement across all four items (68–78%).

Table 3 Responses on Banks funding

Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Banks Funding 1	68	34.3	97	49.0	15	7.6	5	2.5	13	6.6
Banks Funding 2	62	31.3	78	39.4	15	7.6	18	9.1	25	12.6
Banks Funding 3	80	40.4	61	30.8	12	6.1	27	13.6	18	9.1
Banks Funding 4	86	43.4	77	38.9	9	4.5	11	5.6	15	7.6

Respondents largely agreed banks' funding was important, though support was weaker than for government funding, with 62–80% agreeing depending on the item.

Table 4 Responses on International Donors Funding

Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
International Donors Funding 1	96	48.5	76	38.4	10	5.1	3	1.5	13	6.6
International Donors Funding 2	74	37.4	77	38.9	15	7.6	11	5.6	21	10.6
International Donors Funding 3	65	32.8	78	39.4	13	6.6	22	11.1	20	10.1
International Donors Funding 4	59	29.8	92	46.5	18	9.1	14	7.1	15	7.6

Majority responses were positive, with agreement levels between 70–85% across items, though some expressed neutrality or disagreement.

Table 5 Responses on standard of living of small holder farmers

Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
standard of living 1	77	38.9	69	34.8	15	7.6	14	7.1	23	11.6
standard of living 2	82	41.4	84	42.4	10	5.1	17	8.6	5	2.5
standard of living 3	69	34.8	88	44.4	8	4.0	15	7.6	18	9.1

Most respondents agreed that funding improved farmers' living standards, with over 75% support across items.

Table 6 Responses on Asset Based of Small Holder Farmers

Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Asset Based 1	71	35.9	69	34.8	5	2.5	20	10.1	33	16.7
Asset Based 2	63	31.8	72	36.4	18	9.1	16	8.1	29	14.6
Asset Based 3	77	38.9	68	34.3	9	4.5	29	14.6	15	7.6

About 65–73% agreed funding improved farmers' assets, while 15–25% disagreed or were neutral

Table 7 Responses on Income of Small holder Farmers

Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Income 1	67	33.8	85	42.9	9	4.5	20	10.1	17	8.6
Income 2	62	31.3	74	37.4	12	6.1	21	10.6	29	14.6
Income 3	75	37.9	88	44.4	15	7.6	10	5.1	10	5.1

Respondents confirmed that funding increased income, with 70–82% in agreement.

Overall, findings show that government, banks, and international donors' funding significantly improved farmers' living standards, assets, and income. Descriptive results show that all variables had means above 1, indicating positive responses, while standard deviations above 1 suggest variations in opinions. Skewness and kurtosis values

were mixed, but this was not problematic given the large sample size (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013).

Test of hypotheses

Hypotheses one

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between government funding and standard of living of small holder farmers in Imo state

Table 8.1 Model Summary for Hypothesis One Regression Analysis

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df 1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.944 ^a	.891	.890	.44103	.891	1597.282	1	196	.000	.182

a. Predictors: (Constant), government funding

b. Dependent Variable: standard of living

Table 8.3 ANOVA for Hypothesis One Regression Analysis

Table 8.2 ANOVA for Hypothesis One Regression Analysis
ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	310.689	1	310.689	1597.282	.000 ^b
	Residual	38.124	196	.195		
	Total	348.813	197			

a. Dependent Variable: standard of living

b. Predictors: (Constant), government funding

Table 8.3 Coefficients for Hypothesis One Regression Analysis

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.053	.062		.866	.388		
	government funding	1.142	.029	.944	39.966	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: standard of living

Hypothesis one

H01: No significant relationship exists between government funding and standard of living of smallholder farmers in Imo State.

Model summary: R = .944, R² = .891, Adjusted R² = .890, Std. Error = .44103, Durbin-Watson = .182. Government funding

explained 89.1% of the variance in standard of living.

= .944, $t = 39.966$, $p < .001$). H_01 was rejected.

ANOVA: $F(1,196) = 1597.282$, $p < .001$, showing the model fit was significant.

Hypotheses two

H_{02} : There is no significant relationship between Banks funding and the asset based of small holder farmers in Imo state

Coefficients: Government funding significantly predicted standard of living (β

Table 9.1 Model Summary for Hypothesis Two Regression Analysis

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.854 ^a	.730	.728	.76666	.730	528.917	1	196	.000	.063

a. Predictors: (Constant), Banks Funding
 b. Dependent Variable: Asset Based

Table 9.2 ANOVA for Hypothesis Two Regression Analysis

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	310.883	1	310.883	528.917	.000 ^b
	Residual	115.203	196	.588		
	Total	426.086	197			

a. Dependent Variable: Asset Based
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Banks Funding

Table 9.3 Coefficients for Hypothesis Two Regression Analysis

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	.015	.116		.128	.899		
Banks Funding	1.189	.052	.854	22.998	.000	1.000	1.000

Dependent Variable: Asset Based

Hypothesis two

H02: No significant relationship exists between banks’ funding and asset base of smallholder farmers in Imo State.

Model Summary: R = .854, R² = .730, Adjusted R² = .728, Std. Error = .76666, Durbin-Watson = .063. Banks’ funding explained 73.0% of the variance in asset base.

ANOVA: F(1,196) = 528.917, p < .001, confirming a good model fit.

Coefficients: Banks’ funding significantly predicted asset base ($\beta = .854$, $t = 22.998$, $p < .001$). H02 was rejected.

Hypotheses three

H03: There is no significant relationship between international donors funding and income of smallholder farmers in Imo state

Table 10.1 Model Summary for Hypothesis Three Regression Analysis

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.877 ^a	.768	.767	.59887	.768	650.238	1	196	.000	.115

a. Predictors: (Constant), International Donors Funding

b. Dependent Variable: Income

Table 10.2 ANOVA for Hypothesis Three Regression Analysis

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	233.205	1	233.205	650.238	.000 ^b
	Residual	70.295	196	.359		
	Total	303.500	197			

a. Dependent Variable: Income

b. Predictors: (Constant), International Donors Funding

Table 10.3 Coefficients for Hypothesis Three Regression Anal

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	.347	.083		4.182	.000		
International Donors Funding	1.015	.040	.877	25.500	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Income

Hypothesis three

H03: No significant relationship exists between international donors' funding and income of smallholder farmers in Imo State.

Model summary: $R = .877$, $R^2 = .768$, Adjusted $R^2 = .767$, Std. Error = .59887, $p < .001$). H03 was rejected.

The first hypothesis showed a significant positive relationship between agricultural funding and beneficiaries' standard of living. This aligns with Arrow et al. (2012) and Hamilton & Hartwick (2014), but contradicts Pender et al. (2014), likely due to differences in funding patterns and contracts. The second hypothesis revealed that bank funding significantly improved farmers' asset base. This supports the managerial hegemony theory, which suggests that incentives enhance beneficiaries' administrative and productive capacity. The result is consistent with Knutsson (2009), but differs from Booth (2011), Griggs et al. (2013), and Sen (2013). The third hypothesis showed no significant effect of international donor funding on farmers' income. This finding agrees with Ozumba (2014) and Whitfield (2012), but contradicts Collier & Dercon (2014) and Ojiako & Ogbukwa (2012). Variations may

Durbin-Watson = .115. Donors' funding explained 76.8% of the variance in income.

ANOVA: $F(1,196) = 650.238$, $p < .001$, indicating the model was significant.

Coefficients: International donors' funding significantly predicted income ($\beta = .877$, $t = 25.500$,

arise from differences in income measurement approaches. Government funding significantly improved standard of living ($\beta = .944$; $t = 39.966$; $p < .000$). Bank funding significantly improved asset base ($\beta = .854$; $t = 22.998$; $p < .000$). International donor funding showed a significant relationship with income ($\beta = .877$; $t = 25.500$; $p < .000$).

Conclusion

This study investigated agricultural financing and poverty alleviation among smallholder farmers in Imo State using a quantitative survey design. Few prior studies have examined funding sources and their developmental impact at state level in Nigeria. Findings highlight the importance of effective utilization of intervention funds in improving living standards, assets, and income, thereby contributing to poverty reduction, economic

opportunity, and sustainable peace in the region.

Recommendations

Government and stakeholders should strengthen mechanisms that enhance agricultural financing for growth and poverty reduction. Commercial banks and the Central Bank of Nigeria should increase annual credit to farmers at affordable rates. International donors should continue supporting farmers with accessible, low-interest funding.

Contribution to Knowledge

This is the first comprehensive study to disaggregate government, bank, and donor funding in Imo State and assess their distinct impacts.

The study provides new empirical evidence that agricultural funding sources significantly influence smallholder farmers' welfare and development outcomes.

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